

Modelling material flows and cost-benefit of sorting PLA packaging waste in material recovery facilities under different market penetration scenarios

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ABSTRACT

Currently, bio-based and compostable plastic packaging is generally not sorted at material recovery facilities (MRFs) due to its limited market penetration. Instead, such bioplastics are criticised for contaminating other target streams, such as PET bottles at MRFs, yet there is limited evidence to support these claims. This work aims to fill this knowledge gap with a focus on polylactic acid (PLA) packaging waste, by applying a mathematical model to predict the material flow of PLA within MRFs and evaluates the economic viability of bioplastic sorting under different market penetration grades. Our model shows that under current market penetration, the predicted presence of PLA in the PET bottle stream is 7.8 ppm, which is below the suggested threshold concentration without degrading PET recycling (1000 ppm). This still holds true even under high market penetration conditions (200 ppm), assuming that the sorting sequence is adapted to accommodate variations in input waste composition at MRF. The sorting cost of PLA decreases from 906 EUR/t at current market penetration to 170 EUR/t when 1% of post-consumer PLA packaging material is reached at MRF input streams, with an expected break-even point at 2.4%. Moreover, the required PLA volume decreases with increasing near-infrared spectroscopy NIR sorting efficiency alongside the expansion of PLA packaging applications. Furthermore, labour cost, market demand for recovered PLA, and landfill/incineration gate fees are key parameters that substantially affect the cost model result. Overall, the findings from this work suggest that PLA present at MRFs pose no significant issue in current sorting practices, whereas investing in PLA sorting only makes economic sense under strong market growth scenarios of PLA, to achieve circular bioeconomy goals and recycled content targets.

1. Introduction

Global plastics production continues to increase (Geyer et al., 2017), raising widespread concerns about its impacts on ecosystems and human health due to plastic leakage into the environment (Meijer et al., 2021). Based on current production and consumption trends, up to 30 Mt of plastics are projected to leak into aquatic and terrestrial systems by 2040. This aligns with similar trends in the release of microplastics and nanoplastics (MPs/NPs) (OECD, 2024), which primarily originate from

the degradation of mismanaged plastic waste. The occurrence, bio-accumulation, and toxicity of MP/NPs in plants, animals, and humans have been increasingly documented (Lamoree et al., 2025; Munhoz & Beriot, 2025; Roy et al., 2022). Beyond pollution and waste management challenges, the heavy reliance of conventional plastics on fossil-based feedstocks has intensified the efforts to identify more sustainable alternatives (Van Roijen & Miller, 2025). Although materials such as glass, metal, paper, and wool can substitute plastics in certain applications, substituting plastic with such materials often entails

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between 10% to 90% higher greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Meng et al., 2024). Consequently, bio-based and biodegradable plastics have gained increasing attention as a promising strategy to reduce reliance on fossil resources and mitigate the environmental impacts associated with conventional plastics. Bioplastic is a bulk term for polymers that are either bio-based (made from renewable or natural resources) or biodegradable, or both (Dilkes-Hoffman et al., 2019; European Commission, 2022). Although some bioplastics can still be fossil-based, most bioplastics are produced from biomass instead of crude oil, which can result in reduced GHG emissions (Matlar & Ekholm, 2025). For example, the carbon footprint of bio-Polyethylene terephthalate (bio-PET) is 20-50% lower compared to its fossil-based equivalent, whereas polylactic acid (PLA) and starch-based bioplastic achieve, respectively, a 60% and 45% GHG emission reduction compared to PET (Zhu et al., 2016). Further concerns surrounding the potential risk of increasing demand for bio-based plastics on land-use change have been raised, indicating the urgent need for actions to increase the recycling rate for all plastic packaging and to reduce plastic demand for plastic mitigation (Helm et al., 2025).

PLA is a particularly promising biobased and compostable bioplastic, as it is stated to have comparable or even superior properties (strength, gas permeability) compared to conventional plastics (Hamad et al., 2018; Naser et al., 2021). PLA production was 920 ktonne in 2024, accounting for 37% of the entire bioplastic production (European Bioplastic Association, 2024). PLA, amongst other bioplastics, has been used widely in the packaging sector (Karamanlioglu et al., 2017). In the past, strong market growth has been predicted for PLA (Mordor Intelligence; Shen et al., 2009), yet this has not been achieved. Next to higher production cost compared to crude oil-based plastics, other reasons for this lack of market growth are confusion and critical questions about the potential end-of-life (EoL) fate of PLA and its potential circularity.

For example, PLA is an industrially compostable plastic. Yet, depending on the composting conditions and polymer properties such as crystallinity, some composting plants might only achieve incomplete degradation (Mistry et al., 2023; Mouhoubi et al., 2022). This has led to the detection of PLA microplastics in green compost (Bandini et al., 2022; Huerta-Lwanga et al., 2021; Ruggero et al., 2019). Furthermore, due to the minimal recovery of valuable products, composting has been considered the least desirable EoL option for PLA (Rezvani Ghomi et al., 2021). In contrast, mechanical recycling is widely recommended as a primary strategy for managing PLA waste (Cosate de Andrade et al., 2016). This is consistent with previous reports that mechanical recycling is the most energy and environmentally efficient approach for bioplastics (Piemonte, 2011).

PLA, when used in packaging applications, must first be collected and sorted for recycling. However, when collected with organic waste, there is no dedicated PLA sorting process. PLA is typically collected with other lightweight packaging or residual waste, and no dedicated sorting lines for PLA packaging waste are currently installed at MRFs. A combination of processes is used to sort collected post-consumer packaging material at MRFs into different fractions. This includes a series of sieves, air classifiers, and ballistic separators to separate based on the size and shape of objects. In addition, near-infrared spectroscopy (NIR) with a wavelength of 1000-2500 nm, is used to sort specific polymers based on their absorption spectrum (Scott & Waterland, 1995).

Typically, NIR separators are installed for PET, PE, and sometimes PP and PS in many Western European countries. Drop-in bioplastics, e.g., bio-PE and bio-PET with identical chemical structures, can be sorted and recycled with their fossil-based counterparts, however current MRFs lack NIR sorting capacity for bioplastics such as PLA. Concerns have been raised over the last decade that biodegradable/compostable bioplastics may be missorted, ending up in PET and other conventional polymer fractions, degrading the quality of recycled conventional plastics due to material incompatibility (Åkesson et al., 2021; La Mantia et al., 2012; Staplevan et al., 2024). The reported maximum concentration of PLA to avoid decrease in recyclate quality is 10 wt% for PS

(Fraunhofer, 2017), 3 wt% for PP (Fraunhofer, 2017), 2 wt% (Niaounakis, 2013) and 1 wt% (Staplevan et al., 2024) for HDPE, and 0.1 wt% for PET (Alaerts et al., 2018). Other bioplastics, such as polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) and thermoplastic starch (TPS) also show negative influences on the tensile strength and elongation at break of recycled PET (Aldas et al., 2021). However, these reported findings must be interpreted with caution because current washing processes in the recycling plants can remove PLA from lighter polymers (PP, PE) through density separation, and the added flake sorter can further reduce the impurities, which was not discussed in the aforementioned studies. The concern that bioplastics might negatively influence the quality of other polymers is one of the reasons for a stagnated growth of bioplastics in packaging applications, apart from their insufficient technical performance under certain conditions (e.g. barrier, impact strength) (Aramyan et al., 2025).

Sorting trials indicate that PLA items can be sorted out with over 99% efficiency from mixed plastic waste streams, including separation from other polyesters such as PET (Gertman, 2013). PLA can be sorted by NIR into a PLA-specific stream at MRFs, though the current low market penetration of PLA impedes the investments in dedicated NIR equipment at MRFs. Currently, there are limited quantitative studies on this and if the predicted expansion of bioplastics occurs, the question remains at which scale is integrating NIR sorting of bioplastics into MRFs financially justified.

In this context, this study aims to examine the sortability of PLA packaging within MRFs from a technical and economic perspective; applying a predictive sorting model, based on modelling approaches previously described in Kleinhans et al. (2021) and Lase et al. (2022). A business-as-usual (BAU) scenario, in which PLA packaging is a non-target material at MRFs to quantify to what extent PLA contaminates other streams; and scenarios that draw upon predicted increasing PLA market growth. In all these scenarios, the sorting yield and purity of the PLA stream and other target streams are quantified by the predictive model. A cost-benefit analysis was also carried out to help determine the critical mass of PLA needed to make such PLA sorting scenarios economically viable. The high granularity of the modelling approach applied in this work enables broad applicability in future studies and facilitates adaptation to varying waste compositions and sorting configurations.

2. Methodology

2.1. Sorting model

2.1.1. Model structure

The model was developed based on Testa (2015) and Wolf (2011), to predict the mass flow of household packaging waste at a MRF (annual capacity 75 ktonne). The model algorithm was built in Python to allow recirculation loops, together with an Excel interface providing model input, which includes: (i) process sequences in MRFs; (ii) waste categories and quantities (input mass μ^m); (iii) sorting efficiencies q_{ij}^m for each product at each process unit. The predicted output includes: (i) waste composition at each sorting unit and output stream; (ii) recovery rates of targeted waste items; and (iii) quality of the output streams. The model consists of two phases. Phase 1 represents the simplest material flow, which follows sequential operations, whereas recirculation is employed in phase 2 to improve sorting performance (Kleinhans et al., 2021).

Phase 1 can be obtained by:

$$f_j^m = \sum_{i \in N} f_i^m q_{ij}^m \quad (1)$$

Where the flow vector f_j^m represents the mass of waste item m going through process unit j [t/h], q_{ij}^m represents the sorting efficiency, i.e. the fraction of waste item m from process i that ends up in output stream j , N

is the number of sorting processes [-], and m is the number of waste items [-]. For each waste item m , the initial mass entering the entry node i is defined as ($i \in N$):

$$f_i^m = \mu_i^m \quad (2)$$

Input vector μ_i^m represents the input mass of item m at input node i [t/h]. In Phase 1, mass is only entering at the first process step, i.e., the input mass entering the MRF, which is reflected by μ^m . In matrix form, this can be written as:

$$f^m = f^m(Q^m)^T + \mu^m \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} f_1^m \\ \vdots \\ f_N^m \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} q_{1,1}^m & \cdots & q_{N,1}^m \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ q_{1,N}^m & \cdots & q_{N,N}^m \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} f_1^m \\ \vdots \\ f_N^m \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \mu^m \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

or equivalently:

$$f^m = \frac{\mu^m}{I - (Q^m)^T} \quad (5)$$

Q^m is the sorting matrix for waste item m , including sorting efficiencies q_{ij}^m and present how the waste item m is sorted at each sorting unit. T indicates transposed matrix, I is the identity matrix. This solution represents the first-pass material distribution, i.e., before any

Fig. 1. Simplified process flow diagram in material recovery facility for business-as-usual BAU scenario (in which PLA is non-target material), +NIR PLA scenario (highlighted in grey where NIR PLA and PLA stream are added), and case studies. The sorting units highlighted in purple indicate two equally distributed sorting lines, which are designed based on input material flow and throughput. MPO represents the mixed polyolefins.

recirculation is applied.

Phase 2: Recirculation loop

To maximise recovery of valuable materials, a recirculation pathway is implemented. Material from the NIR scavenger unit (process step B) is returned to the magnetic belt (process step A) (Fig. 1). At iteration n , the recirculation mass entering process step A is:

$$f_{recirc,i}^{(n)}[A] = Q_i[A, B] \cdot f_{total,i}^{(n-1)}[B] \quad (6)$$

The recirculated mass is then propagated through subsequent nodes:

$$f_{recirc,i}^{(n)}[j] = \sum_{k=A}^{N-1} Q_i[j, k] \cdot f_{recirc,i}^{(n)}[k] \quad (7)$$

With $j = A+1, \dots, N-1$

Cumulative mass at each node is updated:

$$f_{total,i}^{(n)}[j] = f_{total,i}^{(n-1)}[j] + f_{recirc,i}^{(n)}[j] \quad (8)$$

Iteration continues until the recirculated mass becomes negligible or a maximum of 100 iterations is reached. Convergence is typically achieved within 15-25 iterations.

2.1.2. MRF layout

The layout of MRF is designed based on the collection system in Western European countries (Belgium, Germany, Netherlands, Spain, Denmark, etc.) where plastic packaging waste is collected separately, additionally coupled with industrial feedback on the design (Fig. 1). The annual plant capacity is 75 ktonne, 5400 operating hours with 250 working days per year and 3 eight-hour shifts per day, considering 10% unplanned downtime. The BAU scenario models the material flow of PLA packaging without a NIR PLA installed, whereas in the +NIR PLA scenario additional NIR for sorting PLA is implemented (highlighted in Fig. 1). As the operational capacity of most sorting units is insufficient to treat the whole flow of waste, parallel sorting lines with equal load distribution (highlighted in light purple in Fig. 1) were assumed.

2.1.3. Waste composition

There is no available data regarding the PLA fraction in the current input waste of MRFs. Therefore, in this work, we estimate the expected PLA volume in MRFs based on the fraction of PLA in global plastic production (European Bioplastics, 2024; Geyer et al., 2017), and the fraction of plastic in all packaging applications (70.6%, calculated based on Table S1), assuming same waste generation and collection for sorting rate for both PLA and conventional plastics. Accordingly, it is expected to find 0.12% PLA in the packaging waste in the current MRF input (2023), and 0.41% for the year 2028 with maximum hypothetical growth in the packaging market up to 20%. The PLA market share in the different scenarios was equally divided over 21 selected representative products that were found based on an internet search of current PLA packaging applications (bottles, bags, coffee capsules, etc.), due to a lack of data on existing packaging types which are currently and will be applied in the market. To facilitate illustration, the 21 selected PLA packaging items were grouped into 7 categories: bottles ($n=4$), bowls ($n=3$), trays ($n=4$), cups ($n=3$), films ($n=3$), coffee capsules ($n=2$), and lids ($n=2$) (Table S2). Other representative packaging products (237 items) were selected based on the market data, waste capture rates (Kleinhans et al., 2021; Roosen et al., 2020), and industrial trials (Perfect Sorting Project, 2022). An aggregated version of the data can be found in Table 1.

2.1.4. Sorting efficiency

Table 1 provides an excerpt of the applied sorting efficiency in this work. For non-PLA waste, sorting efficiencies were obtained from a database compiled from previous publications (Kleinhans et al., 2021), and modified based on newer insights from industry feedback and industrial experimental trials. For example, NIR PET sorting efficiency of PET bottles (94%) differs from PET trays (80%) (Table 1), given the

majority of PET trays with complex composition i.e. PE, PP, and ethylene vinyl alcohol EVOH (Roosen et al., 2020).

For selected PLA packaging items, the sorting efficiency of drum screens and ballistic separators were assumed based on the knowledge of waste's physical properties (dimension and weight, Table S2). For example, we assumed that a PLA bottle (500 mL) behaves the same as a PET green tea honey drink (500 mL) in similar dimensions, with 70% possibility to fall into a smaller fraction (40-120 mm) and 30% chance to fall into the fraction >120 mm when it travels through drum screen sections (Kleinhans et al., 2021). Related to the sorting efficiency of different NIR sorting units for PLA packaging items, values were taken from literature presenting sorting trials on different PLA packaging items, in which 1-2% of sorting mistakes of non-PLA NIR units (e.g., NIR PET, NIR PE) were reported (CE Delft, 2021). This is in line with the sorting mistake of NIR for non-target conventional plastics from previous study outcomes (Kleinhans et al., 2021; PerfectSorting project), for example, NIR PS with 1-2% sorting mistake for all non-PS rigid plastics (PET bottle, PET tray, and PE rigid) (Table 1). In this work, a relatively higher sorting mistake of NIR PET was assigned for PLA items (5%) compared to those reported (2%) in CE Delft (2021) to indicate a worst-case scenario. The PLA bottle was assumed to have the same misidentification likelihood (10%) as a HDPE bottle being miss-sorted as PET bottle by NIR PET bottle, due to thick labels, rolling behaviour and item interactions (Kleinhans et al., 2021). This also aligns with the expert judgement from sorting specialists (SUEZ, NTCP) regarding the presence of HDPE bottles in the PET bottle. It is worth noting that operational factors such as belt speed, feedstock composition, and NIR program sequence can affect the sorting efficiency of NIR sorters. These effects were not considered in this study due to data limitations, and future work should examine sorting efficiency under varying operational conditions.

NIR PLA has been reported with 84-99.6% sorting efficiency for PLA items from research and industrial trials (CE Delft, 2021; Gertman, 2013; NatureWorks LLC, 2009; TU Chemnitz, 2017). However, high sorting efficiency may be achieved due to relatively clean input waste streams (small quantities, few categories, and less contamination) in sorting trials compared to collected real waste at MRFs. Thus, moderate sorting efficiency (88%) of NIR PLA for PLA items was selected and applied in the model as a conservative worst-case scenario to mimic the sorting performance under sub-optimal operating conditions. Note that 88% of NIR sorting efficiency was assumed for all selected PLA products regardless of size and shape due to limited primary sorting data, and further research addressing this issue is needed. On these values, an uncertainty analysis was performed to further examine the influence of NIR PLA efficiency on PLA sorting (SI). The low sorting efficiency of NIR PLA was assigned to black PLA items in this work, due to the recognised limitation of NIR sorters on packaging that contains black pigment (Eriksen & Astrup, 2019).

2.1.5. Applied indicators

To evaluate the efficiency of the sorting operation, and to examine whether the sorting facilities meet the output quality requirements for downstream recycling, two indicators are included: 'yield' and 'grade'. The yield (recovery) represents the ratio between the amount of correctly sorted material and the amount of that material in the input waste streams. The grade (purity) represents the fraction of the correctly sorted (desired) materials present in the target stream.

$$\text{Yield} [\%] = \frac{f_z^m}{\mu^m} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Grade} [\%] = \frac{f_z^m}{\sum_1^M f_z^m} \quad (10)$$

f_z^m is the mass of waste items in the target end stream Z [t]. $\sum_1^M f_z^m$ is the total mass of the end stream Z, including both target and non-target

Table 1

Post-consumer packaging material composition (for the year 2023, with 0.12% input PLA) and sorting efficiency. Model input parameters are detailed in the SI. Only one sorting efficiency is shown, as the complementary efficiency equals 100% (e.g., 95% of PET trays to the heavy fraction implies 5% to the light fraction). NIR (+) denotes positive sorting (target removed from non-target), and NIR (-) denotes negative sorting (non-target removed from target, yielding a high-purity stream).

Post-consumer packaging material composition		Sorting units											
Post-consumer packaging material Category	Input share	Air classifier: Heavy fraction	Magnetic belt: Ferrous metal	NIR carton: Drinking carton	Eddy current: Non-ferrous metal	Ballistic Separator: 3D fraction	NIR LDPE (+): PE	NIR LDPE (-): PE	NIR PP: PP	NIR PET: PET	NIR PET bottle: PET bottle	NIR PS (+): PS	NIR PLA: PLA
PET Bottle	22.5%	99.5%	0.2%	2.0%	0.2%	98.6%	5.0%	10.0%	0.8%	93.7%	93.8%	1.0%	1.0%
PET Trays	4.3%	95.0%	0.5%	2.0%	0.1%	55.1%	28.7%	10.0%	0.3%	80.8%	7.8%	1.0%	1.0%
PE rigid	7.7%	99.5%	0.3%	2.0%	0.1%	98.4%	80.0%	98.0%	5.6%	10.0%	10.0%	1.0%	1.0%
PP rigid	10.6%	98.1%	2.0%	2.0%	0.1%	92.0%	0.5%	10.0%	90.0%	10.0%	10.0%	2.0%	1.0%
PS	3.2%	97.2%	0.3%	2.0%	0.1%	88.1%	0.7%	10.0%	0.1%	5.0%	1.0%	88.9%	1.0%
PP&PE Film (multilayer)	5.5%	25.0%	1.0%	2.3%	1.0%	10.0%	26.9%	33.3%	90.0%	1.0%	1.0%	20.0%	1.0%
PE Film (monolayer)	11.0%	28.7%	0.7%	2.2%	0.7%	15.1%	90.0%	90.0%	1.4%	0.8%	1.0%	20.0%	1.0%
Other plastics (multilayer film&PVC)	3.4%	38.9%	0.4%	2.0%	0.1%	26.5%	40.0%	37.7%	0.9%	14.8%	1.1%	0.4%	1.0%
Ferrous metals	19.1%	100.0%	95.0%	0.5%	0.1%	96.4%	0.1%	10.0%	1.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.1%	1.0%
Non-ferrous metals	4.3%	97.0%	0.5%	0.3%	90.0%	30.0%	1.0%	10.0%	1.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.1%	1.0%
Drinking cartons	6.5%	97.0%	0.5%	90.0%	10.0%	20.0%	0.1%	10.0%	0.6%	0.1%	1.0%	0.1%	1.0%
EPS	1.7%	95.0%	1.0%	2.0%	1.0%	80.0%	5.3%	54.0%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	5.1%	1.0%
Selected PLA product													
1 L pasteurised fresh milk bottle	0.006%	99.0%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	10.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Water/juice bottle (250 ml)	0.006%	99.0%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	10.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Water/juice bottle (500 ml)	0.006%	100.0%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	10.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Milk bottle (500 mL)	0.006%	100.0%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	10.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Salad bowl 700 ml	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Black Salad bowl (360 ml)	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	2.0%	0.1%	97.0%	2.0%	2.0%	2.0%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	2.0%
Salad bowl (960 ml)	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Black Sushi tray (with transparent lid)	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	2.0%	0.1%	97.0%	2.0%	2.0%	2.0%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	2.0%
1 L single use tray	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
800 ml Freshfood trays	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Packaging trays with cover 250 ml	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Yogurt cup (115 g)	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
PLA cold drink cup 200 ml	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Sauce cup (15 ml)	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Single-use carrier bag	0.006%	70.0%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	10.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Film for bakery fresh products	0.006%	15.0%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	10.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Carrier bags	0.006%	70.0%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	10.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Post-consumer packaging material composition		Sorting units											
		Air classifier:	Magnetic belt:	NIR carton:	Eddy current:	Ballistic Separator:	NIR LDPE (+):	NIR LDPE (-):	NIR PP: PP	NIR PET:	NIR PET bottle:	NIR PS (+):	NIR PLA:
		Heavy fraction	Ferrous metal	Drinking carton	Non-ferrous metal	3D fraction	(+): PE	(-): PE	PET	PET	PET bottle	PS	PLA
Post-consumer packaging material Category	Input share	Sorting efficiency											
Salad bowl lid 700 ml (3D)	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	90.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Sauce cup lid 15 ml (3D)	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	3.0%	0.1%	90.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
Compatible capsules	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	3.0%	10.0%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%
K-Cup compatible compostable capsule	0.006%	89.3%	0.2%	3.0%	10.0%	97.0%	1.1%	1.1%	1.1%	5.0%	2.0%	2.0%	88.0%

waste items [t]. For the mixed polyolefin MPO (PE&PP multilayer film) stream, the recovery is calculated for MPO alone, whereas the grade is calculated based on both MPO and PE films.

2.2. Economic assessment

A cost-benefit analysis (CBA) was conducted to evaluate which scenario of market penetration, adding small NIR sorter (2.5-3 tph) to target PLA packaging is financially justifiable. The initial investment of the NIR sorter includes capital expenditure (CAPEX) and associated expenses related to installation and contingency. Additionally, since other sorting units, such as the air classifier and ballistic separator, contribute to PLA sorting at earlier stage, the allocated costs were calculated by multiplying the total plant operating cost (excluding associated costs related to adding NIR PLA) by the proportion of sorted PLA waste relative to the total sorting output.

Also, savings from reduced disposal costs that are allocated to other waste treatments (such as incineration and landfilling) for sorting residue, and revenue from sorted PLA were included. Based on the increased material flow at the NIR PLA with gradually increasing PLA market growth, parallel PLA sorting lines equipped with two NIR sorters were assumed to be used when the input PLA reaches 10% or above. Detailed information on cost estimation for the designed MRF can be found in Table 2. Currently, there is no price data available for sorted PLA as it is not traded. Therefore, we assume the market value of 250 EUR/t for a sorted PLA bale based on typical bale prices currently paid in the market for conventional polymers such as PET and HDPE. This is also reliant on the fact that the price of virgin PLA and PLA recyclates from post-industrial waste, is 2400 EUR/t (plasticker.de) and 1100 EUR/t (Karamanlioglu et al., 2017), respectively. The gate fee paid for residue disposal to operators (landfills/incinerators) is set as a constant value (140 EUR/t) for all scenarios. One-at-a-time sensitivity analysis was performed to provide insights into how net cost/profit varies under changing conditions (SI).

$$CAPEX = TIC * CRF + CC \quad (11)$$

$$CRF = \frac{i * (1 + i)^n}{(1 + i)^n - 1} \quad (12)$$

$$SC = \frac{CAPEX + OPEX}{PW} \quad (13)$$

$$SC (PLA) = \frac{CAPEX + OPEX - REVENUE}{output PLA} \quad (14)$$

Where CAPEX represents the annualised capital cost [€], TIC is the

total investment cost [€], CRF is the capital recovery factor, where i is the interest rate of loan (assumed as 5%), n represent the life span of assets (7 years for equipment (three shift operation), 20 year for buildings (Cimpan et al., 2016)). CC denotes annualised contingency cost [€]. OPEX represents operational costs related to labour, electricity, repair & maintenance, insurance, fuel consumption, and disposal of sorting residue. SC represents sorting cost [EUR/t], PW represents processed waste at MRF [t/year]. SC (PLA) represents the economic balance of PLA sorting [EUR/t], in which revenue represents the benefit from disposal savings and selling sorted PLA was included. The cost EUR/t donate to EUR per tonne of output fraction. Revenue from selling other recovered materials is not considered in this work, considering the main focus of this work is on PLA sorting, and to avoid the inclusion of additional uncertain factors in the economic balance.

The cost for transferring sorting residues to incinerators or landfills can vary widely and depends on many factors (local regulations, waste ownership, and contractual arrangements). Hence, this cost which may be incurred by municipalities, waste generators (producers, households), MRF operators, or shared responsibility is not considered in this work. Furthermore, the EPR scheme (extended producer responsibility) shifts the financial responsibility of waste management to producers for waste management. EPR fees are generally collected by the Producer Responsibility Organization (PRO) based on the amount and type of products placed on the market and sometimes combined with eco-modulation, to cover all or part of the real EoL costs related to collection, transport, sorting, and treatment in landfills or incinerators (Tumu et al., 2023). Therefore, incentives from the EPR scheme might foster investment in sorting infrastructure for PLA packaging waste, thereby improving packaging circularity. However, this was not included in this work due to the large variability in EPR schemes across different countries (Pruess, 2023)

2.3. Case studies under high market penetration

For the sake of model simplicity, the sorting sequence is kept fixed. However, this sequence can be adjusted by positioning NIR PLA earlier in the NIR sequence, which becomes particularly relevant when the proportion of PLA in the input waste is high (20%). A supplementary NIR unit can be incorporated to individually sort flexible PLA products, a consideration that becomes increasingly important in case the share of PLA in flexible packaging applications rises. Case 1 represents a modified MRF layout (Fig. 1) in which dedicated NIR sorters for flexible and rigid PLA packaging are positioned immediately after the air classifier and ballistic separator. Case 2 features an adjusted sorting sequence (Fig. 1) in which the NIR PLA is positioned immediately after the NIR

Table 2

Economic assessment with estimated cost parameters to quantify the total capital investment (CAPEX) and total annual operation costs (OPEX) for the business-as-usual BAU scenario under current PLA market penetration (The electricity cost varies between different scenarios and market penetration, detailed information can be found in SI Chapter 3; and labor cost is taken as French case, give that variability of this cost among EU regions, sensitivity analysis of input cost parameters was performed).

Cost Breakdown				
Equipment	Cost	Quantity	Sum	Reference
Loader	€ 312,000	2	€ 624,000	Cimpan et al., 2016a with 30% inflation considered
Bag opener	€ 130,000	2	€ 260,000	Cimpan et al., 2016a with 30% inflation considered
Conveyor belt	€ 16,250	72	€ 1,170,000	Cimpan et al., 2016a with 30% inflation considered
Drum screen	€ 240,000	3	€ 720,000	IFE Aufbereitungstechnik GmbH
Wind shifter (include air compressor system and dust filtration)	€ 240,000	2	€ 480,000	Industrial reference (Kidney S&B)
Over belt magnet	€ 65,000	4	€ 260,000	Cimpan et al., 2016a; Van Camp et al., 2024
Eddy current separator	€ 105,000	2	€ 210,000	Cimpan et al., 2016a; Van Camp et al., 2024
NIR sorter 1.2 m belt width (2.5-3 t/h)	€ 200,000	18	€ 3,600,000	Industrial reference (SUEZ)
NIR sorter 1.6 m belt width (4-5 t/h)	€ 230,000	4	€ 920,000	Industrial reference (SUEZ)
NIR sorter 2.4 m belt width (5-7 t/h)	€ 270,000	2	€ 540,000	Industrial reference (SUEZ)
Air compressor for NIR sorters	€ 39,000	24	€ 936,000	Cimpan et al., 2016a with 30% inflation considered
Ballistic separator	€ 175,000	2	€ 350,000	Model InSystem 001
Cage, bailer & container	€ 276,250	2	€ 552,500	Cimpan et al., 2016a with 30% inflation considered
	SUM (Equipment Costs EC)		€ 10,622,500	
Equipment installation		45.0% of EC	€ 4,780,125	Peters, 2003
Electrical engineering		20.0% of EC	€ 2,124,500	Peters, 2003
Instrumentation and control (automation/control system integration)		10.0% of EC	€ 1,062,250	Lang, 1948 Lang, 1948
Site preparation (grading, drainage)		5.0% of EC	€ 531,125	Peters, 2003
Process buildings (platform, substructures)		12.5% of EC	€ 1,327,813	Peters, 2003
Auxiliary building		12.5% of EC	€ 1,327,813	Peters, 2003
Service facilities (provide power, compressed air, utilities, including office)		40.0% of EC	€ 4,249,000	Peters, 2003
Land (property cost, survey, design)		6.0% of EC	€ 637,350	Peters, 2003
Engineering and supervision		33.0% of EC	€ 3,505,425	Peters, 2003
Construction expenses (temporary office, insurance, accounting, field tests)		39.0% of EC	€ 4,142,775	Peters, 2003
Contractor's fee		17.0% of EC	€ 1,805,825	Peters, 2003
Project management		7.0% of EC	€ 743,575	Industrial reference
	Sum (Total Investment Cost TIC)		€ 36,860,075	Cimpan et al., 2016a
Contingency (unforeseen costs)		10.0% of TIC	€ 3,686,008	Peters, 2003
	Annualised CAPEX		€ 4,224,087	Cimpan et al., 2016a
Labor cost			56,250€ per person per year	Industrial reference & Expert judgement
Electricity (0.162€/kW)			electricity price × electricity consumption (kWh)	Industrial reference & Expert judgement (details can be found in SI Table S14)
Repair and maintenance			6.5% of TIC	Industrial reference & Expert judgement
Insurance			2.0% of TIC	Industrial reference & Expert judgement
Fuel (Diesel, 1600 EUR/m ³)			Fuel price × material load	Cimpan et al., 2016a
Disposal Cost (140 EUR/t)			140 EUR/t × Residue amount (t)	Cimpan et al., 2016a
	Overall Sorting Cost (EUR/t)		€ 186	Overall plant OPEX/plant annual capacity (75 ktonne)

PET. In addition to these two cases that focus on mere positioning, the sorting efficiency of the NIR PLA can also still improve alongside the expansion of PLA packaging applications. Case 3, therefore, represents an optimal scenario relative to Case 2 with enhanced NIR-PLA sorting efficiency (95%) and the inclusion of a PLA recirculation loop.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Yield and grade at 2023 market penetration

The model provides the grade of sorted streams (Fig. 2a), and the yield of input waste per category (Figure S2). The grade of sorted streams of rigid packaging, such as PET bottles and PE rigid, is within the

Fig. 2. (a) Predicted quality of all target streams in business-as-usual scenario (BAU), with comparison of the obtained grade of all streams from the sorting model and the specifications from different PROs, and predicted quality of target streams in +NIR PLA scenario (present in scatters); (b) Simplified material flow of different PLA packaging items in BAU scenario (a), and (c) + NIR PLA scenario; (d) Amount of sorting residue under changing PLA share and plant configuration (BAU and +NIR PLA scenario); (e) PLA weight fraction in the sorted PET bottle stream; (f) PLA weight fraction in the sorted PET tray stream. The dashed line presents the maximum tolerance fraction of PLA without degrading PET recycling. Note that black items and coffee capsules were included in the calculation, thus a lower yield of PLA stream was observed in the + NIR PLA scenario. The 21 applications were grouped into 7 categories for easier visual interpretation. NFe represents non-ferrous metals.

range of 95% and 98%, showing good consistency with the specifications from PROs in countries with stringent sorting requirements, typically met by sequential positive and negative NIR sorting as implemented in the base case sorting plant in this study. The composition of the PET tray and mixed polyolefins accounts for 1.2% and 1% in the sorted PET bottle fraction, resulting in PET bottles fraction with 97.5% purity. Instead, relatively low grades can be observed for MPO (69%) and PE films (86%). This finding is consistent with observations from real waste sampling campaigns conducted in multiple operational sorting facilities (CITEO, 2023), which reported an average purity of 82% for PE film. This is mainly associated with the complexity of flexible packaging, including the presence of multilayer materials that are composed of multiple polymers (e.g., PET/PE, PA/PE), rendering the NIR sorter detection efficiency with overlapping molecular signatures (Lange, 2021; Nemat et al., 2023; Schmidt et al., 2022). This implies the importance of product design for correct sorting, as composite materials have poor classification accuracy (Chen et al., 2021). Furthermore, similar grades of sorting outputs were observed in the +NIR PLA scenario (present as scatter in Fig. 2a). This can be explained by the fact that additional NIR PLA was added at the end of the sorting sequence, which does not affect the sorting performance of the previous processes and thus has a negligible influence (< 0.01%) on overall output grades. This also applies to the similar yields of the respective output fractions that were observed in both scenarios. More detailed model outputs can be found in the SI.

3.2. Flow of PLA packaging items in the 2023 market penetration

Fig. 2b and Fig. 2c shows the mass flow of PLA packaging in different applications under business-as-usual (BAU) and + NIR PLA, respectively. In the BAU scenario, between 97.9% and 99.2% of PLA packaging ends up in the residue fraction along the 21 different products (Fig. 2b). Only a small share of PLA items were present in other valuable streams in both scenarios. In particular, 0.2%, 0.4%, 0.1%, and 0.4% of input PLA items were present in the ferrous metal, MPO, PET bottle, and non-ferrous metal streams, respectively; and less than 0.1% ended up in other streams (Table S9). Detailed information on the fate of non-PLA items can be found in the SI, specifically Table S7 and Table S9. Sorting errors are typically reduced through subsequent positive and negative sorting steps. For instance, an initial 3% mis-sorting of PLA items in the NIR carton unit can be corrected by a cleaner unit, reducing the final PLA contamination in the drinking carton stream to 0.1%. In contrast, even a smaller sorting error at the magnetic belt can result in a higher final contamination level of 0.2% (CE Delft, 2021). This 2-step NIR sorting for each waste fraction to increase the output fractions' quality has been applied in many real sorting facilities (Becidan, 2024). PLA items, such as coffee capsules that contain aluminium, result in a relatively higher sorting mistake in the non-ferrous fraction (Table 1).

In the +NIR PLA scenario, approximately 80-86% of PLA waste (bottles, cups, films, lids) were correctly sorted in the target PLA stream with one NIR sorter added (Table S10), except for black PLA bowl and tray, PLA coffee capsules that show low yields, which result in lower overall yield (70%) of all selected PLA items (Fig. 2c). In particular,

coffee capsules had the lowest yield (26.7%), most likely due to their small dimensions, which results in falling into the fine fraction of the drum screen that is further directed to the residue in our MRF flowsheet. Additionally, rolling behaviour on the conveyor belts, heavy weight, and carbon-black colouration in coffee capsules hinder its overall sorting efficiency. Such results are in line with the Dutch waste management plan, proposing to dispose of plastic coffee capsules in the residual waste or lightweight packaging waste with modified sorting lines (starting from 2026). In contrast, coffee pods made of biodegradable materials can be disposed of with organic waste. Future work could be done to assess ways to separate (biodegradable) coffee capsules from the fine fraction.

Furthermore, colour also plays a role in packaging sortability at MRFs, especially black (Eriksen & Astrup, 2019; Taneepanichskul et al., 2022). Limitations on sorting items that contain carbon black due to its strong absorption of NIR lights has been discussed (Bhuvanesh et al., 2021; Turner, 2018). This explains the relatively low yield of PLA bowls (56.9%) and PLA trays (64.2%) in the +NIR PLA scenario, as it includes dark-coloured items (salad bowl 360 mL and Sushi Tray 1 L). Carbon black should also be avoided, for biodegradable polymers (Heubach GmbH). Additionally, round objects may have relative movement on the conveyor belt compared to square objects, preventing detection and lead to incorrect ejection by the NIR sorter (Jakobs & Kroell, 2024). This is reflected in the lower yield shown for PLA 3D lids (76.3%) in comparison with other PLA packaging applications (bottle). This finding aligns with the on-site observation by Jakobs & Kroell (2024) in a German lightweight packaging sorting plant, where the yield of 3D rolling lids (32.6%) was lower than that of 2D lids (93.9%). These results highlight the importance of packaging design in optimising packaging item sortability in MRFs, also for biodegradable plastics, in case they need to be collected together with other packaging.

The grade of the PLA stream falls within the range of 23.5% to 98.7% with varying input PLA (Table S7). Lower PLA shares on the conveyor belt lead to reduced bale quality due to increased contamination by other materials. Because of lack of a reliable relationship between bale purity and bale price, in the baseline scenario, a fixed bale price of €250 per ton was assumed across all purity levels. While this price is likely overestimated for low-quality bales at low market penetration, it is considered realistic for high market penetration scenarios where purities exceed 90%. To address this uncertainty, a sensitivity analysis was conducted in which bale prices were varied between €0 and €500 per ton. Furthermore, the chance of sorting mistakes might be increased due to potential waste item interaction (overlapping, entanglement). Of this, around 76% contamination in the PLA stream, mostly consisting of PET, PP rigid, other plastics, and PE rigid was found with percentages of 28.2%, 18.5%, 15.0%, and 10.5%, respectively (Table S11). In the scenario where the input PLA increases to 3% and then further to 20%, the model predicts increasing grades, ranging from 89.1% to 98.7%. It should be noted here that the sorting efficiency for NIR PLA (88%) was assumed based on a previous sorting trial (CE Delft, 2021), and PLA yields are associated with this uncertainty. Thus, a Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis was performed to examine the uncertainty of NIR PLA sorting efficiency, with the results presented in SI Figure S3. The mean and median PLA yields (77%) with a slight standard deviation (3%) suggest consistent performance with minimal fluctuations in PLA recovery efficiency. The 5th percentile being 72.2% is quite close to the mean, which further supports the low variability. This indicates that even under unfavourable conditions (e.g., black items, item interactions), the system maintains a baseline yield of ~72%. Detailed information on the distribution of PLA packaging at sorted streams can be found in SI Table S10.

3.3. PLA as 'contaminant' in low and high market penetration scenarios

Fig. 2d illustrates the amount of sorting residue in the +NIR PLA scenario—where PLA packaging is targeted explicitly for

sorting—compared to the business-as-usual (BAU) scenario. In the current BAU scenario, 11.1% of residue was produced at the designed MRF under low market penetration. This residue consists of approximately 19.5% of other plastics, 16.1% PET, and 14.1% EPS, with only 1.1% PLA (Table S9). Under the current PLA market penetration (0.1%), 10.9% of sorting residue was produced at the designed MRF in the +NIR PLA scenario. The reduction of sorting residue in the +NIR PLA scenario compared to that in the BAU scenario becomes more pronounced as the share of PLA in the input waste stream increases. Under the current low PLA input condition, the reduction in sorting residue is modest (1.8%). However, as the PLA share increases from 3% to 20% in the +NIR PLA scenario, the reduction in sorting residue rises substantially from 16.8% to 53.6%. This results in a significant diversion of waste from incineration and landfilling. These findings underscore the importance of implementing dedicated PLA sorting in MRFs as more PLA packaging enters the market. Notably, sorting residue from MRFs is typically sent to landfills or incinerators, incurring disposal costs of approximately 140 €/t. In addition to reducing disposal costs, targeted PLA sorting enhances material circularity and alleviates the demand for virgin PLA production.

When considering the PLA contamination in the PET stream, Fig. 2e indicates that the fraction of PLA packaging in the PET bottle stream in the current scenario of 0.12% market penetration results in a contamination of 0.00078% (7.8 ppm). Knowing that the quality requirement for the PET bottle is high ($\geq 97\%$) according to PROs (CITEO, 2024; *Fost Plus*, 2019) and La Mantia et al. (2012b), we can conclude that in the current scenario, no significant effect of PLA on PET recyclates can be expected. This finding accords with a multi-year sorting study, which showed that PLA packaging is present at a level of less than 0.048% (480 ppm) in the sorted PET stream (Gertman, 2013). Instead, the model output (SI, Table S9) suggests that the main contributor to the 2.3% impurity in the PET bottle stream is PET trays. The fraction of PLA in PET tray stream is shown in Fig. 2f; it remains below 0.1% until PLA reaches a market penetration of 5% in the packaging market. A larger fraction of PLA was present in the PET tray stream (from 7.8 ppm to 0.1% with input PLA share increase from 0.12% to 5%, respectively), because of the relatively small quantity of PET tray (4.3%) in the input considering how the fraction was calculated.

These results are in contrast to the expressed concern by the National Association for PET container resources that PLA containers jeopardise the PET recycling system, along with reduced recyclate quality (NAPCOR, 2014). Our model includes a high 'worst case' sorting mistake (5%) of PLA products on the NIR PET compared to what was reported from sorting trials (2%) (CE Delft, 2021) and 0.04% (Gertman, 2013); so it is unlikely that PLA packaging would be problematic for PET recycling. This observation was also made by Thoden van Velzen et al. (2022), who highlight that no negative impact of PLA food trays on PET bottle recycling is expected under the current operation practice at MRFs with rigorous NIR systems. Equally, PET recyclers often still apply NIR flake sorting, which would further reduce this problem.

Important to note that this result is only valid for PLA based on PLA sorting trials reported, and thus cannot be transferred to other bioplastics, especially polyesters with aromatic groups such as PBAT, which might give more similarities to conventional plastics (e.g., PET) in the NIR spectrum.

3.4. Case studies: exploring model applications

Similar grade and yield were observed for most sorted streams across the different scenarios, except for PLA and PS (Figure S3). The remarkable improvement in grade value of the sorted PS stream primarily results from reduced PLA contamination (Fig. 3a). With a low PS input, even minor decreases in PLA mis-sorting lead to a pronounced grade increase of the sorted PS stream. In all case studies, the grade of the sorted PLA fraction remained above 95% across all scenarios, with only a 0.1% grade reduction in case 3 and a 3% grade reduction in case 1

Fig. 3. Selected results in different scenarios under high PLA market penetration (20%).

(Fig. 3b).

For PLA, changes in the sorting sequence led to noticeable variations in yield (Fig. 3c). Specifically, the PLA yield decreased from 69.7% in the +NIR PLA scenario (NIR PLA placed before NIR scavenger) to 67.3% in Case 2 (NIR PLA placed immediately after NIR PET). This can be explained by a relatively high sorting error of the NIR PET for PLA packaging assumed (5%), reducing the flow of PLA passing through the NIR PLA for subsequent recovery. Whereas, a slightly higher yield (70.3%) of PLA can be found in Case 1, when the NIR PLA unit was positioned immediately before NIR PET. The presence of PLA in the sorted PET bottle stream decreased to 0.02% in Case 1 compared to 0.14% in the +NIR PLA scenario (Fig. 3d). This is consistent with what was reported in CE Delft (2021), that sorting PLA before PET can reduce PLA contamination in the PET bottle stream (below 0.02%–0.03%). A noticeable improvement in PLA yield was observed in Case 3, where a higher NIR PLA efficiency (95%) and PLA recirculation were assumed, resulting in a 12.8% increase relative to the +NIR PLA scenario.

3.5. Economic analysis

3.5.1. Economic viability with changing PLA share

A detailed cost breakdown of capital investment and operation cost (e.g., labour, electricity, etc.), and costs comparison between BAU and +NIR PLA scenario can be found in SI Table S14 and Figure S4. Under the BAU scenario, the fixed capital cost of the defined sorting plant, encompassing, amongst others, process equipment, site and civil works, installation, and engineering (Table S12), is estimated at 40.6 million EUR. This estimate aligns with reported costs for plants of comparable capacity (PreZero, 2022; TOMRA Systems ASA, 2022; TriPlast GmbH, 2024). In the +NIR PLA scenario, the extra capital expenditure for adding NIR PLA includes the costs of equipment, installation, and project management, particularly, 449,768 EUR for adding one NIR PLA, and 899,536 EUR for two NIR PLA when the input PLA reaches 10% and above. Under the current market penetration, the overall plant OPEX increased from 9.7 million EUR in the BAU scenario to 9.9 million EUR in the +NIR PLA scenario, resulting in the plant's overall sorting costs increasing from 186 EUR/t to 190 EUR/t (Fig. 4a). The calculated sorting cost, though higher than the previously reported sorting cost

(179 EUR/t) in Belgium by Marques et al. (2014), is reasonable considering inflation and increased energy costs. A lower overall sorting cost is observed in the +NIR PLA scenario (189–196 EUR/t) compared to the BAU scenario (191–207 EUR/t) when input PLA reaches 5% and above, despite the increased OPEX in the +NIR PLA scenario. This is attributed to the decreased disposal cost resulting from the deduction of sorting residue in the +NIR PLA scenario under all market penetration scenarios, as discussed above (Fig. 4). For the sorting cost of PLA shown in Fig. 4a, a steep decrease from 1260 EUR/t to 580 EUR/t was observed when the input PLA increased from 0.12% to 1%, followed by a moderate decrease with increasing market penetration (from 349 EUR/t at 3% to 248 EUR/t at 20%). The relatively higher PLA sorting cost compared to the overall sorting cost even under high market penetration, can be explained by the low yield of PLA (~70%). This is because the relatively higher sorting mistake of NIR PLA was assumed for PLA items in this work (12%), and PLA was designed not to be recirculated as other valuable materials (e.g. PET and PE rigids, drinking cartons, etc.) for improving the yields (Table 1). A higher yield of PLA can be achieved with improved NIR PLA sorting efficiency as simulated in case 3 (Fig. 3b), resulting in more revenue and less PLA needed to justify the investment in sorting PLA (Fig. 4f). Fig. 4b shows the cost-benefit analysis of PLA sorting in the +NIR PLA scenario where PLA input increases from 0.12% (2023) to 20% (future). The benefits of PLA sorting from disposal saving and selling PLA bales were included in this estimation, accordingly, lower PLA sorting costs can be observed compared to those in Fig. 4a. In the baseline scenario (0.12% input PLA), the annualised CAPEX for PLA sorting is 63,554 EUR, annual OPEX is 266,278 EUR. This was dominated by labour cost (168,750 EUR), followed by electricity (51,613 EUR) and repair and maintenance (28,917 EUR); revenue from disposal saving and selling sorted PLA was 20,772 EUR and 66,842 EUR, respectively (see Table S15 in SI). In a 75 ktonne per year sorting plant with 0.12% input, the output fraction of PLA is 0.08%; translating this to the 241,218 EUR net cost (total cost – revenue), this comes at a PLA sorting cost of 906 EUR/t. This accounts for 23.2% of the green dot fee set by Belgian PRO for compostable and biodegradable plastic packaging (3909.2 EUR/t), which categorised as obstructive packaging (Fostplus, 2025). The EPR fee is country-specific, and a reduced fee for compostable and biodegradable plastic was found in

Fig. 4. (a) Sorting cost of different scenarios with changing market penetration, (b) Cost benefit analysis of PLA sorting cost, revenue includes selling sorted PLA stream and disposal saving compared to BAU; Cost-benefit analysis of PLA sorting under $\pm 25\%$ variation of (c) labor cost, (d) market value of sorted PLA and (e) disposal cost for sorting residue. Critical mass of needed PLA to achieve profitable PLA sorting at MRF with annual processing capacity of 75 ktonne, with variation in (f) NIR PLA sorting efficiency, (g) market value of sorted PLA and disposal cost for sorting residue. Note that the cost EUR/t donate to EUR per tonne of output fraction. The x-axis scales in panels (a–e) are intentionally varied to allow clearer visualisation of trends.

Italy (130 EUR/t) (CONAI, 2025) and Spain (216 EUR/t) for single-use plastic packaging) (Ecoembes, 2025). The calculated cost in this work excludes collection, transport, and other PRO-associated costs, which means that, indeed in the current market penetration scenario, investing in PLA sorting is not economically viable in countries with lower EPR fees for compostable plastic packaging. However, this cost can be significantly reduced to 170 EUR/t when the PLA share reaches 1% in the input waste streams, if the associated revenue from disposal savings and selling sorted PLA is taken into account. As reported in earlier studies, sorting costs are correlated with MRF scale (Bünemann et al., 2011; Cimpan et al., 2016), which implies that a centralised PLA sorting facility can be an alternative option when low PLA volume discourages PLA sorting investment.

Furthermore, the profit from selling sorted PLA combined with savings due to reduced disposal costs of sorting residues equals the total

costs for sorting PLA for a PLA input share of approximately 2.4% at MRF (Fig. 4b). This corresponds to 10.45 Mt PLA packaging placed on the market (assuming 50% of produced PLA is applied in packaging), which can be achieved by 2034 based on the predicted growth rate of PLA (CAGR 36.65%) from European Bioplastics and by 2069 based on the less optimistic CAGR (12.5%) from a PLA production company (TotalEnergies Corbion, 2020). Profitable PLA sorting of 83 EUR/t of sorted PLA was observed when PLA reached 3%, particularly, the total costs and revenue are 524,041 EUR and 670,904 EUR, respectively. The estimated critical mass of PLA at MRF input for profitable PLA sorting falls within the range (2–16%) reported in literature (CE Delft, 2019). The difference might be attributed to the selected larger annual processing capacity (75 ktonne) of MRF in this work compared to that in the previous study (20 ktonne–30 ktonne), which is in line with reported reduced sorting costs associated with increasing sorting plant capacity

(Cimpan et al., 2016).

Overall, the results from this work show that the current PLA market is too small to justify the associated costs of sorting PLA, and the key driver for PLA sorting investments is a considerable amount of PLA present at MRFs. Profitable PLA sorting can be achieved when PLA reaches over 2.4% at MRF, as present in Fig. 4b. It is worth noting that costs related to waste collection and transport, and subsidies from the EPR scheme for PLA sorting are not considered in this work, which varies depending on the collection system (curbside collection or drop-off system), collection frequency (weekly or biweekly), and different PRO regulations (Zhang & Wen, 2014). Additionally, the ownership of sorted materials at MRFs depends on regulation and contract, whereas this was assumed to be combined with disposal savings in the benefit analysis for PLA sorting in this work.

3.5.2. Sensitivity analysis of cost parameters

Sensitivity analysis was performed to account for the variation in input cost parameters (modified by $\pm 25\%$), and to determine their impact on the profitability of PLA sorting. The net PLA sorting cost is sensitive to several cost parameters that are assumed in the cost-benefit analysis under both low and high market penetration (Figure S6). Among these, labour cost has a more important influence on the net PLA sorting cost in the current scenario with low market penetration (Fig. 4c), followed by equipment cost, the price of electricity, and the market value of sorted PLA. Particularly, the net PLA sorting cost falls within the range of 746 EUR/t to 1066 EUR/t when varying labour cost by $\pm 25\%$ (Figure S6). This indicates that the high economic feasibility of PLA sorting is more favoured in countries with cheap labour or fully automated MRFs (PreZero, 2021). Other associated cost parameters (price of fuel, project management, contingency, maintenance) have minor contributions ($< 1\%$) to the change of net PLA sorting cost under increasing market penetration (Figure S6). However, under high market penetration, the market value of sorted PLA and the disposal fee for sorting residue have a greater impact compared to other cost parameters (Fig. 4d and Fig. 4e). This is because both parameters are positively correlated with the revenue obtained from selling the sorted PLA stream and savings from reduced disposal costs. Specifically, for a 25% increase in the market value of sorted PLA (313 EUR/t), the revenue from the sorted PLA stream increased by 19.9% from 2.65 to 3.31 million EUR when 20% of PLA is present in the input waste stream at MRF. Consequently, the benefit of sorting per tonne of PLA increased from 198 EUR to 233 EUR. The NIR sorting efficiency for PLA can be improved with advancements in sorting techniques, thus higher grade and yield of PLA can be expected accordingly, resulting in more revenue and less PLA needed to justify the investment in sorting PLA (Fig. 4f).

With the increasing PLA market, the market value of sorted PLA and the disposal cost for sorting residue present the highest impact on the profitability of PLA sorting. As discussed above, a critical mass of PLA is needed to justify the investment in PLA sorting. The needed PLA volume is negatively correlated with the market value of sorted PLA, and the disposal cost of sorting residue. The sorting residue from MRFs is sent to landfills or incinerators for energy recovery, which incur different expenses depending on the region and regulations. For example, in Europe, prices may range from 65 EUR/t to 254 EUR/t for incineration and 30 EUR/t to 200 EUR/t for landfills (European Investment Bank, 2024). In countries with lower disposal costs for sorting residue, a larger volume of PLA is required to justify investments in PLA sorting (Fig. 4g). The price of sorted PLA is correlated with the market price of virgin PLA, which is also subject to market demands and regulations on bioplastics. Specifically, if subsidies are provided for recycling PLA or penalties are incurred for not recycling, a lower PLA volume will be needed to achieve financial justification. Restrictions on single-use plastics and EPR schemes may further support the expansion of the PLA market. In contrast, when no market exists for sorted PLA, the required PLA volume exceeds 30% of the total waste at the defined MRF.

4. Model limitations

This study is based on a sorting model, whereas flows in real operating MRFs are dynamic, fluctuating with time due to the heterogeneity of collected packaging waste (Curtis et al., 2021; Perera et al., 2025), and operating conditions (e.g., conveyor belt speed), which can be adjusted to optimise the efficiency of MRFs. Given the limited available data, it was assumed that the incoming feed stream and the processing of different types of waste occurred under steady conditions. In addition to the overall composition of waste, other factors also influence the efficiency of sorting equipment, such as belt speed and load, the program of the NIR, surface contamination (food residue) on (bio)plastics, or even partial polymer degradation (Mhaddolkar et al., 2024). Future work could focus on further including such variations on the sorting efficiencies.

In this work, we assume that PLA sorting happens shortly after collection to achieve accurate classification with NIR. With limited information available regarding NIR sorting efficiency for heterogeneous PLA packaging products, the same sorting efficiency of the PLA NIR has been used for different PLA waste regardless of size, shape, or label. The manual sorting by skilled labour at the end of sorting output streams to improve the yield and purity of valuable materials was also not considered in this work.

5. Conclusion

This work applied a comprehensive mathematical model using flow-based analysis and cost-benefit analysis to access how PLA packaging behaves at MRF under current and increased market penetration. Based on the performed material flow modelling, approximately 70% of PLA waste can be recovered through the implementation of NIR PLA, thereby diverting the PLA from disposal in incineration or landfill. Results showed that under current market penetration, the presence of PLA in the PET bottle stream is 7.8 ppm. The fraction of PLA in all valuable streams remains below the reported maximum tolerance of PLA even under the BAU scenario (no dedicated PLA sorting line) with high PLA market penetration. This study counters previous claimed concerns that bioplastics deteriorate the quality of recovered material at MRFs. The disturbance is not higher than other plastic types present in packaging. Conclusions from this study are only valid for PLA with a well-distinguishable NIR spectrum compared to other plastics, including PET, and cannot be transferred to other bioplastics, as this would require NIR experiments to assess sorting efficiencies and errors.

Findings from the coupled CBA model suggest that it is both technically and economically feasible to utilise NIRs for PLA sorting when PLA reaches 2.4% of input waste at MRFs, which can be achieved by 2034 under the most optimistic prediction of PLA production (CAGR 36.65%). The sorting costs for PLA under the current PLA market penetration with revenue from selling sorted PLA at a price of 250 EUR/t are 906 EUR/t. This can be significantly reduced to 170 EUR/t when PLA reaches 1% of input waste at MRFs. Furthermore, a lower required PLA quantity for profitable PLA sorting is achievable if there is an increase in landfill/incineration fees and the market value of sorted PLA, and if the EPR fee charged from the producer to cover packaging waste management is included. Overall, this work provides evidence about PLA packaging material flows at MRFs, which can be used to feed the debate about the potential future of PLA in the packaging market and potential future scenarios in which PLA can be effectively sorted without disturbing the reprocessing of other plastics.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Wang Li: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alexandra Schmuck:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Louis Van Caelenberg:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Virginie Decottignies:** Writing – review & editing. **Hy Boui Chang:** Writing – review & editing. **Adeline Dupas:** Writing – review & editing. **Peter Ragaert:** Writing – review & editing. **Shreyash Anil Gujar:** Writing – review & editing. **Marcel C P van Eijk:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Steven De Meester:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Steven De Meester reports financial support was provided by Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU). Given Steven De Meester role as editor for Resources, Conservation and Recycling, had no involvement in the peer review of this article and had no access to information regarding its peer review. Full responsibility for the editorial process for this article was delegated to another journal editor. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2026.108811](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2026.108811).

Data availability

Data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article and its supplementary materials.

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